
OP 105

Strengthening Communicable Disease Surveillance through a Simplified Complementary Digital Dashboard at Colombo Regional Directorate of Health Services

Muthahhara M¹, Liyanage ADMD¹, Gajanayake C¹, Weerasooriya SD¹, Perera GAC², Liyanapathirane TV¹, Niranjala Perera², Maduranga MAVA¹

¹Office of Regional Director of Health Services - Colombo, ²Office of Provincial Director of Health Services - Western Province

Introduction

- Colombo RDHS area consists of 19 MOHs
 - Estimated Population - 1,845,010
 - High communicable disease burden
 - Demands continuous attention at district, provincial and national levels.
-

High communicable disease burden

Dengue

Source: NaDSys surveillance, (as of 14.07.2025 midnight)

Tuberculosis

Total No. of cases - 4608

Colombo district - 1088 (23.6%)

Colombo RDHS - 585 (12.7%)

Source: <https://tb.epims.health.gov.lk/> (as of 15.07.2025)

Patients Overview by Clinic Centers

Leprosy

Total No. of cases - 621

Colombo RDHS - 71 (11.4%)

	District	No. cases (01.01.2025 - 30.06.2025)
1	Batticaloa	76
2	Colombo RDHS	71
3	Gampaha	58
4	Kurunegala	47
5	Kalutara	44
6	Polonnaruwa	33
7	Matara	31
8	Galle	30
9	Puttalam	25
10	Anuradhapura	23
11	Ratnapura	22
12	Kandy	21
13	CMC	20
14	Hambantota	19
15	Badulla	18
16	Ampara	17
17	Jaffna	13
18	Kalmunai	13
19	Trincomalee	12
20	Kegalle	10
21	Monaragala	5
22	Vavuniya	4
23	Matale	4
24	Kilinochchi	2
25	Nuwaraeliya	2
26	Mullativ	1
27	Mannar	0
Total		621

Timely indicators benefit the community

- Enable early detection and response.

Risk of diverted focus

- Without strict monitoring, institutions may shift attention to other areas due to unexpected issues.

The solution:

- A sustainable, simple and integrated system
- Ensures timely action and sustained focus.

Background

Communicable disease surveillance in Sri Lanka is supported by multiple vertical programmes:

- TB and Leprosy have separate databases and programme structures
- The Epidemiology Unit manages diseases including the 12 diseases which require special surveillance.

A complementary digital dashboard was introduced to:

- Track timeliness of special investigations.
- Consolidate data from institutions for dengue, TB and leprosy.
- Enable timely action and in-depth analysis of disease epidemiology.

Description of the intervention/initiative

A dashboard was developed at the Colombo RDHS for each MOH area.

The dashboard covered the entities of 12 diseases requiring special investigations, along with dengue, tuberculosis and leprosy - all of which has a higher disease burden in Colombo.

MOH Boralesgamuwa - Weekly Epid Summary 2025

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MOH Boralesgamuwa - 2025																					
Period	Jan-25		Feb-25		Mar-25		Apr-25		May-25		Jun-25		Jul-25		Aug-25		Sep-25		Oct-25		
Diseases	Notified	Confirmed																			
Chicken pox	1	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Measles	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Leptospirosis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mumps	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Encephalitis	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Viral Hepatitis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Whooping Cough	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rubella	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Enteric Fever	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tetanus	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Leishmaniasis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meningitis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	1	1	5	4	0	0	0	0	1	0	0										

Weekly Investigation Breakdown

District Performance MOH Boralesgamuwa Weekwise 41

Individual level data were made available for leprosy and tuberculosis

Data entry was facilitated from both district and MOH level to ensure completeness of database and timely intervention

This also facilitated contact tracing.

Patient's Name	Register Date	Disease Type	MOH	GN/Ward	Name of Contact	Age	Gender	Date of Screen	Relationship	Address	Contact No
IERIF REKUMUDU	2025-01-04	PTB - Bacteriologica	MOH Area Egodaunya		2024COL1955 contacts			2025-01-15		25/1 USWATTE LANI	C1
BERT WITHANAGI	2025-01-08	PTB - Bacteriologica	MOH Area Egodaunya	Egoda Uyana South	No Contact						
ALUWATHTHAGE	2025-01-30	PTB - Clinically Diagnosed	MOH Area Egodaunya	Egoda Uyana North	Chathuranga	30	Male	2025-03-11		14/11 SUBHA SADAI	C1
					Shavan	7	Male	2025-03-11		14/11 SUBHA SADAI	C2
					Chandana	50	Male	2025-03-06		235,Bodhiraja Mw,V	C1
					Anusha	54	Female	2025-03-06		235,Bodhiraja Mw,V	C2
					Vinuki	16	Female	2025-03-06		235,Bodhiraja Mw,V	C3
Shamarakkalage	2025-02-14	EPTB - Clinically Diagnosed	MOH Area Egodaunya	Indibedda West	Lakshiluni	7	Female	2025-03-06		235,Bodhiraja Mw,V	C4
R. MAHAMARAKK	2025-02-05	PTB - Clinically Diagnosed	MOH Area Egodaunya	Indibedda West	2024COL1233contacts			2025-03-05		67/88/B, BACK WAT	C1
					Suranga	46	Male	2025-03-11		12/55,USWATHTHA	C1
					Pasindu	19	Male	2025-03-11		12/55,USWATHTHA	C2
DIKA NILANTHI	2025-02-20	PTB - Bacteriologica	MOH Area Egodaunya		Kusumawathi	71	Female	2025-03-11		12/55,USWATHTHA	C3
					Chaminda	50	Male	2025-03-05		56/58,St. PETER'S LA	C1
					Tharushi	25	Female	2025-03-05		56/58,St. PETER'S LA	C2
					Subashini	24	Female	2025-03-05		56/58,St. PETER'S LA	C3
					Dinuka	16	Male	2025-03-05		56/58,St. PETER'S LA	C4
					Theruli	12/12	Female	2025-03-05		56/58,St. PETER'S LA	C5
SHAMANDIGE PRI	2025-03-03	PTB - Bacteriologica	MOH Area Egodaunya	Moratuwella West	Sriyani	75	Female	2025-03-05		56/58,St. PETER'S LA	C6

Serial number	Updating Date	Source of notification (IPF/Data base)	MOH area	Name	Age	Sex	Address	Notifying Institution	MDT Date	IPF Available (Yes/No)	Red Copies Sent (Yes/No)	MOH Investigation Date	No contacts traced	Remarks
1	07.01.2024	IPF	Egoda uyana	K.D.Sriyani	63	F	35/17 Uswatta road,Moratuwa	CSTH	04.01.2024	Yes	Yes	2025.01.10	2	
2	2025.02.7	IPF	Egoda Uyana	Suresh perera	45	M	51/01,Willorawatta moratuwa	B.H.Panadura	24.01.2025	Yes	Yes	2025.01.15	2	
3	2025.03.03	IPF	Egodaunya	Anul kaliyaya	51	F	301,Egodaunya modara	B.H. Panadura	03.03.2025	Yes	Yes		6	
4	2025.03.26	IPF	Egoda Uyana	D.Sandamali	44	F	08,Dinasiri mawatha,Egoda uyana, Moratuwa	CLC	03.03.2025	Yes	Yes		4	1 contact positive
5	2025.04.15	IPF	Egoda Uyana	Shashika Dilrukshi	23	F	97/43,Lucky sewana Road, Egodaunya	Panadura B.H	11.03.2025	Yes	Yes			
6	2025.04.18	IPF	Egoda Uyana	Lahiru Chathuranga	20	M	91/31,Lucyseverepuram, Egodaunya, Moratuwa	Panadura B.H		Yes	Yes		3	
7	2015.04.20	IPF	Egoda Uyana	kawshiya anagi	12	F	51/1,Padukka Ididbedda,Moratuwa	Panadura B.H		Yes			2	1 contact positive
8	2025.04.23	IPF	Egoda Uyana	Madhusanka Shehan	32	M	51/1,Padukka Ididbedda,Moratuwa	Panadura B.H		Yes				
9	2025.04.28	IPF	Egoda Uyana	M.D.Mathusan	40	M	72/8/A, Madis RD,Willarewatta,Moratuwa	CLC		Yes				
10	2025.06.08	IPF	Egoda Uyana	Senuki Vihansa	7	F	23/91,Jucky sewenpura,Egodaunya	Panadura BH		Yes			5	
11	2025.06.08	IPF	Egoda Uyana	Jerad Silva	61	M	No-63/04, Jayanthi mw,Egodaunya	Panadura B.H		Yes				
12	2025.06.22		Egoda Uyana	Ashalon Shrayel	11	M	55/1,5,Lane,Kohelawella							
13	2025.06.22		Egoda Uyana	Senudi Fernando	11	F	10A,Vihara mw,Koralawella							
14	2025.06.22		Egoda Uyana	Chandima Darshana	43	M	65/10,2nd lane Rawathawatha, Moratuwa	CLC	14.03.2025	Yes	Yes		4	
15	2025.06.22		Egoda Uyana	Harsha FRDO	43	M	No-3/3,St perers Rd,Moretuwella, Moratuwa	Panadura B.H		Yes			2	
16	2025.06.22		Egoda Uyana	P.K.Lakshan	23	M	136/21,Sharamadeka mw,Koralawella, Moratuwa	CSTH	23.04.2025	Yes			0	UT
17	2025.06.22		Egoda Uyana	Rashika wasanthi	46	F	25,Francisco place, Moretuwella,Moratuwa	CSTH	07.05.2025	Yes			0	
18	2025.06.22		Egoda Uyana	M.T.Prasath Indikka Coorvey	46		14/1,Lower ididbedda, Bambatuwa 2nd Rd,moretti						8	

These are complementary to the electronic data systems of national level institutions

- e-Surveillance
- NadSys
- PHSMIS (ALC)
- TB dashboard

National Dengue Surveillance System

National Dengue Control Unit
Ministry of Health

e - SURVEILLANCE

WEB BASED NATIONAL COMMUNICABLE DISEASE SURVEILLANCE SYSTEM

Epidemiology Unit - Ministry of Health - Sri Lanka

However, PHI-level data are currently not available in these systems.

There is a need to operationalize data collection at the PHI level to enable tracking of case investigations and to identify if the same cases remain pending.

A more organized and integrated approach is required to improve timeliness and completeness of surveillance data.

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		Awaiting Investigation Breakdown																										
No.	Week	1		2		3		4		5		6		7		8		9		10		11		12		13		
		Dengue	Other	Dengue	Other	Dengue	Other	Dengue	Other	Dengue	Other	Dengue	Other	Dengue	Other	Dengue	Other	Dengue	Other	Dengue	Other	Dengue	Other	Dengue	Other	Dengue	Other	
1	Pepiliyana	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	Rattanapitiya	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
3	Boralesgamuwa A	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
4	Boralesgamuwa B	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	Werahera	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	Katuwawala	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	Total	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	0	2	2	0	1	0	0	2	0

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	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
18	Notifications total for the year										
19	WEEK		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
20	1. Dengue		9	8	2	4	6	3	5	5	4
21	2. Leptospirosis		0	0	0	2	0	0	0	2	0
22	3. Dysentery		0	0							
23	4. Tuberculosis		3	1							
24	5. Chicken pox		0	0							
25	6. Food Poisoning		0	0							
26	7. Meningitis		0	0							
27	8. Mumps		0	0							
28	9. Measles		0	0							
29	10. Encephalitis		0	0							
30	11. Enteric Fever		0	0							
31	12. Leishmaniasis		0	0							
32	13. Leprosy		1	0							
33	14. Viral Hepatitis		0	0							
34	15. Conge Rubella S		0	0							
35	16. Simple Contd.Fever		0	0							
36	17. Human Rabies		0	0							
37	18. Whooping Cough		0	0							
38	19. Tetanus		0	0							
39	20. Acute Flaccid Paralysis		0	0							
40	21. Malaria		0	0							

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	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
51	Confirmed cases total for the year								
52	WEEK		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
53	1. Dengue		6	7					
54	2. Leptospirosis		0	0					
55	3. Dysentery		0	0					
56	4. Tuberculosis		2	1					
57	5. Chicken pox		0	0					
58	6. Food Poisoning		0	0					
59	7. Meningitis		0	0					
60	8. Mumps		0	0					
61	9. Measles		0	0					
62	10. Encephalitis		0	0					
63	11. Enteric Fever		0	0					
64	12. Leishmaniasis		0	0					
65	13. Leprosy		1	0					
66	14. Viral Hepatitis		0	0					

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	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	
30	Pending cases																		
31	WEEK		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
32	1. Dengue		0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	2	2	0	0	2	0	3	0	
33	2. Leptospirosis		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
34	3. Dysentery		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	
35	4. Tuberculosis		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	
36	5. Chicken pox		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
37	6. Food Poisoning		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
38	7. Meningitis		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
39	8. Mumps		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
40	9. Measles		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
41	10. Encephalitis		0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
42	11. Enteric Fever		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
43	12. Leishmaniasis		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
44	13. Leprosy		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
45	14. Viral Hepatitis		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
46	15. Conge Rubella S		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
47	16. Simple Contd.Fever		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
48	17. Human Rabies		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

The completeness and timeliness of investigation of all notified diseases were monitored in depth up to PHI area level

Methods used for the evaluation

- ✓ Timeliness of investigations (including Leprosy and TB)
- ✓ Completeness of special investigation forms
- ✓ Percentage of dengue outcome entered on NadSys

were used as indicators for performance evaluation.

Disease	SI forms due	SI forms received	Pending
Chicken pox	4	4	0
Measles	1	1	0
Leptospirosis	5	5	0
Mumps	0	0	0
Encephalitis	1	1	0
Viral Hepatitis	0	0	0
Whooping Cough	0	0	0
Rubella	0	0	0
Enteric Fever	0	0	0
Tetanus	0	0	0
Leishmaniasis	0	0	0
Meningitis	0	0	0
Total	11	11	0

MOH area	Cases in 2025 upto 24th March	Outcomes entered in NadSys	%
MOH-Battaramulla	143	140	97.90
MOH-Boralesgamuv	63	57	90.48
MOH-Dehiwala	89	69	77.53
MOH-Egodauyana	50	42	84.00
MOH-Gothatuwa	222	170	76.58
MOH-Hanwella	64	57	89.06
MOH-Homagama	86	61	70.93
MOH-Kaduwela	169	157	92.90
MOH-Kahathuduwa	100	61	61.00
MOH-Kesbewa	62	53	85.48
MOH-Kolonnawa	122	100	81.97
MOH-Maharagama	152	130	85.53
MOH-Moratuwa	63	62	98.41
MOH-Nugegoda	117	102	87.18
MOH-Padukka	38	35	92.11
MOH-Piliyandala	66	55	83.33
MOH-Pitakotte	95	70	73.68
MOH-Rathmalana	133	120	90.23
Grand Total	1834	1541	84.02

Progress Review of Communicable Disease Activities

RDHS COLOMBO
15.05.2025

Regular “Progress Review of Communicable Disease Activities” meetings were conducted weekly online with MOHs and supervisory officers

These discussions also facilitated 2-way feedback

Results

The dashboard enhanced real time identification of issues and prompt response

Reduced administrative burden at both district and MOH level by building up accountability through 2-way communication

Completeness of SI form submission has reached 100%

For TB and leprosy delays in notification has been avoided by real time data sharing (which is important for prevention and control of diseases)

Data gaps between national database and MOH database has been minimized.

Dengue outcome data entry improved from 43.3% in early February to 86.6% by the end of March 2025.

Lessons learnt and Conclusions

Low cost simplified digital dashboards that enable monitoring of selected aspects complementary to the national e-platforms enhance completeness, timeliness and coordination of events at district and MOH level.

Acknowledgement

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PDHS

Thank You